

THE EFFECT OF SERVICE QUALITY ON THE SATISFACTION OF PROTOCOLAN SERVICE USERS IN THE BANJARBARU CITY, INDONESIA GOVERNMENT

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Abstract:

The scope of protocol assignments is reflected in several types of activities such as preparation for the implementation of events, reception/audience, travel leaders in and outside the country/region, arranging meetings/hearings, and conducting ceremonies. The role and function of the protocol also determines the success of an institutional activity even more so that it is attached to the leader because it will create a social order that brings one another closer, creates a ceremony that is wisdom and order, also creates order in carrying out activities. So that we need the best performance and service in order to create satisfaction for protocol service users, one of which is to pay attention to the quality of service through excellent service indicators. This study aims to analyze the effect of service quality consisting of variables reliability, responsiveness, assurance, empathy and tangibles both partially and simultaneously on satisfaction of protocol service users in the Banjarbaru City Government and to find out which variables are the most dominant influence on satisfaction of the service. The method used in this study is a quantitative method, with a population of 54, a sample of 54 people and data analysis techniques with research instruments validity test, reliability test, classical assumption and using multiple linear regression. The results of this study indicate that the variables reliability, responsiveness, assurance, empathy and tangibles partially have a significant effect on satisfaction of protocol service users in the Banjarbaru City Government, all these independent variables have a significant influence on the dependent variables simultaneously and variables that dominant influence on satisfaction of protocol service users in the Banjarbaru City Government is responsiveness, adjusted determination (R^2) is 0.511 or 51.1%, this shows the amount of contribution given by all independent variables to the dependent variable. Some suggestions from this study include improvements to the services provided by the variables of reliability, responsiveness, assurance, empathy and tangibles, and

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suggestions for future research. It is expected that adding other variables can be known which variables have a significant effect on the satisfaction of protocol service users.

Keywords: service quality, service user satisfaction, protocol

1. Introduction

Protocol is regulated in international agreements and laws and regulations in each country, in Indonesia the protocol is regulated in Undang-undang Nomor 9 Tahun 2010 concerning Protocol, Undang-Undang Nomor 23 tahun 2014 concerning Regional Government, and Peraturan Pemerintah Nomor 62 tahun 1990 concerning Protocol Provisions Regarding Layout, Ceremonies, and Respect Arrangements. The scope of protocol that is the duty of the protocol is reflected in several types of activities that must be carried out such as reception/audience, guest visits, leadership trips at home and abroad, regional meetings, meetings, meals and ceremonies. The role and function of the protocol also determine the success of an institutional activity even more so that it is attached to the leader because it will create a social order that draws closer to each other, creates a ceremony that is disciplined and orderly, also creates order and security in carrying out an activity leader. Often most people understand the protocol as an presenter/MC even some say the protocol is only as a regulator of the problem of the program, even though the protocol also serves in administrative matters such as meeting notes, manuscripts of approval/official notes, agreement texts, layout, ceremonial order, and reverence and arrange the event.

In addition, protocol must also have good service quality where quality is said to be good when protocol performance is in line with the expectations of service recipients or leaders. Not infrequently found protocol activities not in accordance with the expectations and desires of service recipients/leaders while on the other hand the protocol is tasked with carrying out and regulating the course of activities in a professional manner where the course of activities must be in accordance with the expectations of service recipients/leaders. Therefore, the protocol in this case carrying out protocol duties is required to have broad capabilities and knowledge related to protocol activities. Protocols are also required to have high loyalty because they see such a broad task where in the implementation of their duties a protocol cannot estimate the time of duty and does not even know the time of holiday, moreover the tasks that involve meals, work visits, and reception of guests who can come continuously.

In Banjarbaru City, Protocol assignments were in the Public Relations and Protocol Section of the Banjarbaru City Regional Secretariat in the Protocol Subdivision. Where the main task of the Banjarbaru City protocol is listed in the Peraturan Walikota Banjarbaru Nomor 8 Tahun 2017 concerning the Details of Implementing Tasks at the Regional Secretariat of Banjarbaru City. The Sub Division of Protocol is held by 1 (one) echelon IV official with a total of 6 civil servant staff and 6 non PNS staff.

The function of leadership facilitation, official travel, banquets, reception of work visits, reception of state guests, ceremonies, layout, organizing events, MCs, event organizers, meeting arrangements, and coordination of activities outside the region is the task of the Protocol Sub Division as a task protocol. Referring to the DPA Protocol Subdivision, protocol activities tend to increase every year. When compared to the standard number of employees in the protocol field that should be more than now there is clearly a gap, not to mention the implementation of administrative and reporting tasks. In their daily lives, it is not uncommon to find multiple workloads where an employee must carry out two tasks at once.

In addition, assistance in the implementation of protocol education or training in improving the quality of the resources of the protocol apparatus itself is also still minimal, this is none other than the lack of government and private support in conducting protocol training. The absence of operational standard procedures for the Protocol Subdivision and still referring to UU No. 9 Tahun 2010 concerning Protocol and PP No. 62 Tahun 1990 concerning Protocol Provisions concerning Spatial Planning, Ceremonies, and Respect Regulations is also an obstacle to the implementation of protocol duties so that the quality of protocol services is considered to be less than optimal or not as expected. This is done to optimize the performance of protocols to stay in line with the quality of service expected by service recipients/leaders. Therefore, to find out how well the protocol performance carried out by the Protocol Sub-Section requires an assessment of the quality of services provided and felt by service recipients.

2. Research Framework

Protocol performance is a matter that must be considered in the implementation of protocol services because it is one of the good evaluations or protocols of the Banjarbaru City Regional Secretariat to carry out its duties and functions in serving protocol service users. The better the performance is shown, the better the assessment of service users on the protocol of the Regional Secretariat in carrying out its duties and functions. But in its implementation, it often faces obstacles both internally and externally which become obstacles to the implementation of protocol duties so that the protocol must take steps in order to optimize protocol performance in anticipating existing problems for performance achievement in Banjarbaru City.

Service quality is an indicator of assessment of public services provided by public bodies, which through the assessment of the quality of service of a public body can find out the extent to which the service has been given to the wishes of the customer/service recipient. The quality of protocol services provided by the protocol of the Regional Secretariat depends on the protocol performance itself. Where service quality is said to be good if the performance is carried out in accordance with expectations, if the performance is less than expected then the quality of service is said to be bad, and if the performance performed exceeds the expectations of service users

then the service quality is said to be very good. Service quality factors that will influence the satisfaction of protocol service users are described as follows:

Description:

—————>: Partial

- - - - ->: Simultaneous

From the analysis model above, it can be explained that service quality (variable X) affects individually (partially) towards satisfaction or dissatisfaction with protocol service users. Where when service quality is perceived in accordance with expectations, service users will be satisfied, and vice versa if service quality is perceived to be far from expectations, service users will become dissatisfied.

2.1 Research Hypothesis

Based on this frame of mind, the hypothesis can be proposed as follows:

H0: There is a partially significant effect of the variable reliability on Protocol Service User Satisfaction in the Banjarbaru City Government;

Ha: There is no partial significant effect of the variable reliability on Protocol Service User Satisfaction in the Banjarbaru City Government;

H0: There is a partially significant effect of the responsiveness variable on Protocol Service User Satisfaction in the Banjarbaru City Government;

Ha: There is no partial significant effect of the responsiveness variable on Protocol Service User Satisfaction in the Banjarbaru City Government;

H0: There is a significant effect partially from the assurance variable on Protocol Service User Satisfaction in the Banjarbaru City Government;

Ha: There is no partial significant effect of assurance variable on Protocol Service User Satisfaction in the Banjarbaru City Government;

H0: There is a significant partial effect of the empathy variable on Protocol Service User Satisfaction in the Banjarbaru City Government;

Ha: There is no partial significant effect of the empathy variable on Protocol Service User Satisfaction in the Banjarbaru City Government;

H0: There is a significant partial effect of tangibles on Protocol Service User Satisfaction in the Banjarbaru City Government;

Ha: There is no significant partial effect of tangibles on Protocol Service User Satisfaction in the Banjarbaru City Government;

H0: There is a simultaneous significant effect of all service quality variables on the satisfaction of protocol service users in the Banjarbaru City Government;

Ha: There is no simultaneous significant effect of all service quality variables on the satisfaction of protocol service users in the Banjarbaru City Government.

3. Methods

This study uses an associative causal method. Associative research will know the relationship between two or more variables that can explain the symptoms. This study examines the effect of Service Quality variables namely Reliability (X1), Responsiveness (X2), Assurance (X3) and Emphaty (X4) and Tangibles (X5) on Service User Satisfaction (Y). The research population as well as the study sample were recipients of protocol services, namely each of the leaders of the regional work unit in the Banjarbaru City Government as many as 54 people. Data collection in this study was carried out through field studies, namely data collection with direct observation of objects. Data collection was done through questionnaires, observations using performance instruments according to Prawirosentono and service quality according to Parasuraman, and documentation as secondary data.

4. Results

4.1 Descriptive Analysis of the Answers of the Respondent's Questionnaire

Recapitulation of respondents responses aims to describe the overall research variables, both in the number of respondents (people), and in the percentage numbers of the items of the research variables Supriyanto and Machfudz (2010), while the frequency of respondents' answers to questions of variables Reliability, Responsiveness, Assurance, Empathy, Tangibles and Protocol Service User Satisfaction as follows:

Respondent's answer										
Item	1 (STS)		2 (TS)		3 (N)		4 (S)		5 (SS)	
	f	%	f	%	F	%	f	%	f	%
X1.1	0	0	5	9,3	8	14,8	12	22,2	29	53,7
X1.2	1	1,9	4	7,4	8	14,8	12	22,2	29	53,7
X1.3	0	0	4	7,4	9	16,7	11	20,4	30	55,6
X1.4	1	1,9	4	7,4	10	18,5	5	9,3	34	63
X2.1	4	7,4	1	1,9	8	14,8	12	22,2	29	53,7
X2.2	4	7,4	1	1,9	3	5,6	21	38,9	25	46,3
X2.3	4	7,4	1	1,9	3	5,6	20	37	26	48,1

X3.1	2	3,7	6	11,1	14	25,9	21	38,9	11	20,4
X3.2	4	7,4	7	13	9	16,7	11	20,4	23	42,6
X3.3	3	5,6	8	14,8	11	20,4	12	22,2	20	37
X3.4	3	5,6	5	9,3	11	20,4	18	33,3	17	31,5
X3.5	3	5,6	4	7,4	9	16,7	27	50	11	20,4
X4.1	3	5,6	3	5,6	7	13	15	27,8	26	48,1
X4.2	2	3,7	5	9,3	6	11,1	10	18,5	31	57,4
X4.3	1	1,9	6	11,1	4	7,4	16	29,6	27	50
X5.1	2	3,7	5	9,3	12	22,2	9	16,7	26	48,1
X5.2	2	3,7	4	7,4	10	18,5	13	24,1	25	46,3
X5.3	2	3,7	4	7,4	8	14,8	15	27,8	25	46,3
Y.1	0	0	0	0	9	16,7	24	44,4	21	38,9
Y.2	0	0	0	0	8	14	24	44,4	22	40,7
Y.3	0	0	1	1,9	5	9,3	33	61,1	15	27,8

4.2 Test Validity and Reliability

The question of the independent variable and dependent is valid if it has a value of $r > r$ requirements, the research instrument can be said to be valid if the correlation coefficient > 0.3 is valid. Test Reliability is done with the aim to test whether it can be trusted. In this study the reliability value of an instrument is accepted if it has a Cronbach Alpha of at least 0.6. Arikunto in Supriyanto and Machfudz (2010), it can be concluded that all question items are reliable (reliable or trusted). Based on the results of the SPSS calculation, the validity test of all question items has a correlation value > 0.3 , so that all items can be valid. Based on the results of the Reliability Test all instruments were acceptable because of Cronbach's Alpha $> 0,6$. It can be concluded conclusively.

4.3 Heteroskedastisitas Test

According to the results of heteroscedasticity test, this study is free from heteroscedasticity due to the spread of points and points forming a pattern so that it meets the pretest requirements for multiple regression requirements, namely the classical assumption of heteroscedasticity.

4.4 Normality test

Based on the results of the normality test, it is declared free and can be used for research because the point around the line does not spread to others, so that the pre test requirements for multiple regression requirements are classic assumptions of normality.

4.5 Multicollinearity Test

Multicollinearity test is conducted to determine whether there are equations in the independent variable. Variable Inflation Factor (VIF) and the Tolerance value of the dependent variable on the independent variable the comparison of VIF and Tolerance values as follows:

Variable	VIF	Tolerance	Description
X ₁ Reliability	1,050	0,953	Multicollinearity does not occur
X ₂ Responsiveness	1,137	0,880	Multicollinearity does not occur
X ₃ Jaminan	1,092	0,916	Multicollinearity does not occur
X ₄ Emphaty	1,063	0,940	Multicollinearity does not occur
X ₅ Tangibels	1,042	0,960	Multicollinearity does not occur

The test results show a VIF value of no more than 5 and if the regression model has a VIF value below the value of 5 and has a Tolerance number close to 1, then the regression model is free from the problem of Multicollinearity (Santoso, 2005).

4.6 Multiple Linear Regression

The hypothesis is tested with a confidence value of 95% or a significance value of 0,05 ($\alpha = 0,05$). To examine the truth of these hypotheses, multiple linear regression analysis is used. In this regression analysis will be carried out concurrent test or F test as well as partial or t test.

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Variable	Regression Coefficient (bi)	t count	t table	Beta	sig
Constant	1,746				
Reliability (X1)	0,172	3,520	1,678	0,364	0,001
Responsiveness (X2)	0,234	3,817	1,678	0,411	0,000
Assurance (X3)	0,099	2,744	1,678	0,289	0,009
Empathy (X4)	0,160	2,615	1,678	0,272	0,012
Tangibles (X5)	0,135	2,306	1,678	0,238	0,026
Constant = 1,376		F count = 10,026			
Multiple R = 0,715		F Table = 2,410			
R square (R ²) = 0,511		Sig = 0,000			

The recapitulation results are seen as R Square of 0,511, which means the magnitude of the variation in the contribution of all the independent variables to the dependent variable is 51.1% while the remaining 48.9% is explained by other reasons outside of this study.

The regression equation is as follows:

$$Y = 1,746 + 0,172 X1 + 0,234 X2 + 0,099 X3 + 0,160 X4 + 0,135 X5 + ei \quad (1)$$

Based on these equations, it shows that all independent variables have a positive regression coefficient. This means the variable Reliability (X1), Responsiveness (X2), Assurance (X3), Empathy (X4), Tangibles (X5) has a relationship in the same direction or proportional to the dependent variable or User Service Protocol Satisfaction (Y). That is, if the variables X1, X2, X3, X4 and X5 increase, the dependent variable Y also increases, and if the variables X1, X2, X3, X4 and X5 decrease, the dependent variable Y will decrease.

- a) The value of Constant 1,746 means that if there is no independent variable, then Protocol Service User Satisfaction is 1,746.
- b) Value of X1 = 0,172 means that if the Reliability variable increases by one, then Protocol Service User Satisfaction increases by 0,172.
- c) Value of X2 = 0,234 means that if the Responsiveness variable increases by one, then Protocol Service User Satisfaction increases by 0,234.
- d) X3 value = 0,099 meaning that if the Assurance variable increases by one, then Protocol Service User Satisfaction increases by 0,099.
- e) Value of X4 = 0,160 meaning that if the Empathy variable increases by one, then Protocol Service User Satisfaction increases by 0,160.
- f) X5 value = 0,135 meaning that if the Tangibles variable increases by one, then Protocol Service User Satisfaction increases by 0,135.

Interpretation of constants (1,746) in this research using a Likert scale with a value of 1 to 5 so that it cannot be said if the variables Reliability, Responsiveness, Assurance, Empathy, Tangibles have a value of 0, this is because the three variables cannot be worth 0 because of the Likert Scale the lowest used is 1 and based on the results of the calculation of version 21.0 of SPSS in this study the constant value is 1,746 and is included in the very strong category.

4.7 Hypothesis Testing

A. Test of Hypothesis I: Partial Test t

Through this test, it can be seen whether the variables consisting of Reliability, Responsiveness, Assurance, Empathy, Tangibles have a partially significant effect on the Banjarbaru Protocol Service User Satisfaction, that is by comparing the probability value of the variable with a probability of 5% ($\alpha = 0,05$) if the probability significance value is $< (\alpha = 0,05)$ then there is a significant effect on the dependent variable, and vice versa, and $df = n - K - 1 = 54 - 6 - 1 = 47$, then the t value of the table is 1,678 As for the results of statistical calculations can be seen in the table below:

Independent Variable	t count	t table	Sig.	Description
X1 Reliability	3,520	1,678	0,001	Significant
X2 Responsiveness	3,817	1,678	0,000	Significant
X3 Assurance	2,744	1,678	0,009	Significant
X4 Emphaty	2,615	1,678	0,012	Significant
X5 Tangibels	2,306	1,678	0,026	Significant

B. Test of Hypothesis II: Simultaneous F Test

Based on the results of calculations through SPSS show F count of 7,798 and F table can be with $df 1 = K - 1 = 6 - 1 = 5$ and $df 2 = n - K = 54 - 6 = 48$ then the value of F table is 2,410 and if significance $< 0,05$. It can be concluded that the independent variables together have an influence on the dependent variable, based on the theory, the value of sig F count is $0,000 < 0,05$ and F count $7,798 > 2,410$. On the basis of these comparison, H_a is rejected so that it can be concluded all service quality items consisting of Reliability, Responsiveness, Assurance, Empathy and Tangibles simultaneously have a significant effect on User Satisfaction of Protocol Services in the Banjarbaru City Government can be accepted or tested.

5. Discussion

The statements of hypotheses 1, 2, 3, 4, and 5 that the variables Reliability, Responsiveness, Assurance, Empathy, Tangibles have a significant effect on Protocol Service User Satisfaction in the proven Banjarbaru City Government. The first factor, namely the reliability concluded by employees in providing services to Protocol Service Users, is something that Protocol Users need, such as the timeliness of service, without any differences in service, sympathy and high level of job accuracy so protocol service users are satisfied when receiving protocol services. The responsiveness factor of an employee in providing services to Protocol Service Users is needed by SKPD Leaders such as delivering procedures, ease of access and readiness of employees in providing services. Factor Assurance shows that protocol service users need security in the form of assurance such as good communication, quality, competence and courtesy in providing services. The fourth factor, empathy of an employee such as the ability to

serve, understand and be willing to spend time for Protocol Service Users in providing services to Users in order to achieve customer/customer satisfaction. The fifth factor, tangibles which is a tangible form of physical evidence is that there is a comfortable and adequate Public Relations and Protocol Office, adequate equipment and so on. The findings of this study are in line with the results of previous research by Rozak (2018). The results showed that the tangible, assurance, reliability, empathy, and responsiveness variables simultaneously (together) had an effect on the service satisfaction of the ITS Surabaya Protocol Sub Unit. This is based on the calculation of SPSS where F count is 24,279 greater than F table of 2,31. Partially tangible, empathy, assurance, and responsiveness have a positive and significant influence on service satisfaction of the ITS Surabaya Protocol Sub Unit. While the reliability variable has a positive but not significant effect. Empathy variable has the most dominant influence on service user satisfaction of ITS Surabaya Protocol Sub Unit with a value of standardized beta coefficients of 0,262.

The results of other studies namely Rosyid (2014) explain the variables of empathy and assurance which have a positive and significant influence on customer satisfaction. But the responsiveness, tangible, and reliability variables have a positive but not significant effect. The coefficient of determination (R²) of 0,549 explains that 54,9% of customer satisfaction is based on the variables tangible, reliability, responsiveness, assurance and empathy. Whereas 45,1% of customer satisfaction is determined by other variables not examined in this study as Lovenia (2012) research found the results of research testing hypotheses with the t test explaining the independent variables proved to have a significant influence on the dependent variable of customer satisfaction. Through the f test, it can be seen that physical evidence, reliability, responsiveness, assurance and awareness variables influence the dependent variable of customer satisfaction. Adjusted R Square number is equal to 0,779 which indicates that the service quality variable is able to explain together customer satisfaction at 77,90%, while the rest is influenced by other variables not examined, such as promotions, interest rates and others, variables that dominant is reliability.

The sixth hypothesis statement that all service quality variables have a significant simultaneous effect on Protocol Service User Satisfaction in the Banjarbaru City Government is proven. This can be seen from the results of the calculation that produces the value of sig F count is 0,000 < 0,05 and F count 7,798 > 2,410 so it can be concluded that all service quality items consisting of Reliability, Responsiveness, Assurance, Empathy, Tangibles have their respective roles and functions to achieve the satisfaction of protocol service users in the Banjarbaru City Government.

6. Conclusion

Based on the test results, all independent variables (service quality) consisting of Reliability, Responsiveness, Assurance, Empathy, and Tangibles showed a positive and significant effect partially on the satisfaction of protocol service users in the Banjarbaru

City Government. The variable that most influences the satisfaction of protocol service users in the Banjarbaru City Government is caused by the responsiveness variable with a regression coefficient of 0.234 (2.34%). The coefficient of determination (R²) produced is 0.511, which means the amount of variation in the contribution of all independent variables to the dependent variable is 51.1% while the remaining 48.9% is explained by other reasons not examined in this study.

6.1 Suggestions

Based on the results of the research and discussion, as a suggestion for improving service to the object of research, the future should be needed to improve:

1. Reliability of employees in the Public Relations and Protocol Section of the Banjarbaru City Secretariat, such as the timeliness of service, the same service without distinguishing the Leadership Group of Regional Work Units in the Banjarbaru City Government, a sympathetic attitude towards SKPD Leaders in the Banjarbaru City Government, and the level accuracy is good and has supported the achievement of protocol service user satisfaction but it would be better to continue to be improved and improved in completing work.
2. Responsiveness of employees in the Public Relations and Protocol Section of the Banjarbaru City Secretariat, such as the delivery of information needed by the Head of the Regional Work Unit in the Banjarbaru City Government, the ease of SKPD Leaders in the Banjarbaru City Government in meeting service officers. The readiness of employees in serving SKPD leaders in the Banjarbaru City Government has also been very evident, this can be seen from the Responsiveness variable being the most contributors in service user satisfaction, but it will be better to be repaired every year.
3. Service assurance in the Public Relations and Protocol Division of the Banjarbaru City Secretariat, such as good communication with SKPD leaders in the Banjarbaru City Government, has high credibility, security, competent service officers and polite and courteous service officers when serving SKPD leaders in Banjarbaru City Government to be further improved.
4. In addition to Reliability, Responsiveness and Assurance, Empathy employees in the Public Relations and Protocol Section of Banjarbaru City Regional Secretariat, such as having understanding and knowledge of SKPD Leaders in Banjarbaru City Government, understanding the needs of SKPD Leaders in Banjarbaru City Government and having a comfortable operating time for SKPD Leaders in the Banjarbaru City Government.
5. Tangibles have a significant effect on the satisfaction of SKPD Leaders in the Banjarbaru City Government. Tangibles need attention when all four variables can be repaired in the form of improving physical facilities such as office buildings, parking lots, and clean and tidy toilets. In addition, the technological equipment used in the Public Relations and Protocol Section of the Banjarbaru City Secretariat, as well as the appearance of neat, polite and appropriate service

personnel will be better patched and will further increase the satisfaction of protocol users in the future.

References

- Lovenia, Christiana Okky Agusta. 2012. Pengaruh Kualitas Pelayanan Terhadap Kepuasan Nasabah Bank Jateng Cabang Utama Semarang. *Undergraduate thesis*, Universitas Diponegoro. Semarang.
- Peraturan pemerintah Nomor 62 tahun 1990 tentang ketentuan Keprotokolan Mengenai Tata Tempat, tata Upacara, dan Tata Penghormatan.
- Peraturan Walikota Banjarbaru Nomor 8 tahun 2017 Tentang Rincian Tugas Pelaksana Pada Sekretariat Daerah Kota Banjarbaru.
- Rosyid, Wahidur. 2014. Pengaruh Kualitas Pelayanan Terhadap Kepuasan Nasabah Pembiayaan (Studi Kasus BPRS Situbondo). *Undergraduate thesis*, Universitas Islam Negeri Sunan Kalijaga. Yogyakarta.
- Rozak, Abdul. 2018. Pengaruh Kualitas Layanan Terhadap Kepuasan Pengguna Jasa Sub Unit Protokoler Institut Teknologi Sepuluh Nopember Surabaya. *Undergraduate thesis*, Universitas 17 Agustus 1945. Surabaya
- Santoso, Singgih. 2005. *Statistik Parametik*. PT Gramedia Pustaka: Jakarta.
- Supriyanto, Achmad Sani and Masyhuri Machfudz. 2010. *Metodologi Riset: Manajemen Sumberdaya Manusia*. Malang: UIN-Maliki Press.
- Undang-undang Nomor 23 tahun 2014 tentang Pemerintah Daerah.
- Undang-undang Nomor 9 Tahun 2010 tentang Keprotokolan.

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